

The (a, d) -Ascending Subgraph Decomposition

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Abstract: Let G be a graph of size q and a, n, d be positive integers for which $\frac{n}{2}[2a + (n - 1)d] \leq q < \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)[2a + nd]$. Then G is said to have (a, d) -ascending subgraph decomposition $((a, d)$ -ASD) if the edge set of G can be partitioned into n -non-empty sets generating subgraphs $G_1, G_2, G_3, \dots, G_n$ with out isolating vertices such that each G_i is isomorphic to a proper subgraph of G_{i+1} for $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $|E(G_i)| = a + (i - 1)d$. In this paper, we find (a, d) -ASD for $K_n, K_{m,n}$ and for product graphs.

Key Words: ASD, (a, d) -ASD, Smarandachely (P, Q) -decomposition, Smarandachely (a, d) -decomposition.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph we mean a finite undirected graph without loops or multiple edges. A wheel on p vertices is denoted by W_p . A path of length t is denoted by P_{t+1} . A graph obtained from two graphs G_1 and G_2 by taking one copy of G_1 (which has p -vertices) and p copies of G_2 and then joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 to every vertex of the i^{th} copy of G_2 is denoted by $G_1 \odot G_2$. Terms not defined here are used in the sense of Harary [4]. Throughout this paper $G \subset H$ means G is a subgraph of H .

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple graph of order p and size q . If $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ are edge disjoint subgraphs of G such that $E(G) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \dots \cup E(G_n)$, then $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is said to be a decomposition of G .

The concept of ASD was introduced by Alavi et al. [1]. The graph G of size q where $\binom{n+1}{2} \leq q < \binom{n+2}{2}$, is said to have an ascending subgraph decomposition (ASD) if

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G can be decomposed into n -subgraphs $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ without isolated vertices such that each G_i is isomorphic to a proper subgraph of G_{i+1} for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. We generalize the concept of ASD as follows:

Definition 1.1 *A graph G has a Smarandachely (P, Q) -decomposition for graphical properties P and Q , $P \subset Q$ if the edge set $E(G)$ can be partitioned into non-empty sets generating subgraphs $H \in P$ without isolating vertices such that each such H is isomorphic to a proper subgraph of $J \in Q$. In particular, we define a Smarandachely (a, d) -decomposition is a Smarandachely (P, Q) -decomposition, where $P = \{G_j / |E(G_j)| = a + (j-1)d\}$ and $Q = P = \{G_{j+1} / G_j \in P \text{ and } |E(G_{j+1})| = a + jd\}$ into subgraphs $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$.*

In other words G is a simple graph of size q and a, n, d are positive integers for which $\frac{n}{2}[2a + (n-1)d] \leq q < \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)[2a + nd]$. Then (a, d) -ascending subgraph decomposition $((a, d) - ASD)$ of G is the edge disjoint decomposition of G into subgraphs $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ without isolated vertices such that each G_i is isomorphic to a proper subgraph of G_{i+1} for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and $|E(G_i)| = a + (i-1)d$. The following theorems will be useful in proving certain results in Section 2.

Theorem 1.2([1]) *Let G be a graph of size q , where $\binom{n+1}{2} \leq q < \binom{n+2}{2}$ for some positive integers n , such that G has an ascending subgraph decomposition $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ such that G_i has size i for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and G_n has size $q - \binom{n}{2}$.*

Theorem 1.3([2]) *$C_n \times C_n$ is decomposed into two Hamilton cycles if n is odd.*

Theorem 1.4([2]) *K_n is (i) decomposed into $\frac{n}{2}$ -Hamilton cycles if n is odd. (ii) decomposed into $\left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \right\rfloor$ -Hamilton cycles and a 1-factors if n is even.*

§2. Main Results

Definition 2.1 *Let G be a graph of size q and a, n, d be positive integers for which $\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)[2a + (n-1)d] \leq q < \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)[2a + nd]$. Then G is said to have (a, d) -ascending subgraph decomposition $((a, d) - ASD)$ if the edge set of G can be partitioned into n non-empty sets generating subgraphs $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ without isolated vertices such that each G_i is isomorphic to a proper subgraph of G_{i+1} for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and $|E(G_i)| = a + (i-1)d$.*

Remark 2.2 From the above definition, the usual ASD of G coincides with $(1, 1)$ -ASD of G .

Example 2.3 Consider the Graph G .

Fig.2.1

Clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, G_3\}$ is a $(1, 2)$ -ASD of G .

Theorem 2.4 Let G be a graph of size q , where $\binom{n}{2} [2a + (n-1)d] \leq q < \binom{n+1}{2} [2a + nd]$ for some positive integer n , such that G has (a, d) -ASD, then G has an (a, d) -ASD $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ such that G_i has size $a + (i-1)d$ for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and G_n has size $q - \binom{n-1}{2} [2a + (n-2)d]$.

The following number theoretical result will be useful for proving further results.

Lemma 2.5 Given that the numbers $a, a + d, a + 2d, \dots, a + (n-1)d$ are in A.P ($a, d \in \mathbb{Z}$). Then their sum is

- (i) $S_n = (a - d)n + d \binom{n+1}{2}$ if $d \leq a$ and
- (ii) $S_n = a \binom{n+1}{2} + (d - a) \binom{n}{2}$ if $d \geq a$.

§3. (a, d) -ASD on Complete Graphs and Complete Bipartite Graphs

Theorem 3.1 K_{n+1} has (a, d) -ASD if and only if $a = 1, d = 1$.

Proof Suppose the graph K_{n+1} has (a, d) -ASD $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ with $|E(G_i)| = a + (i-1)d$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

By (ii) of Lemma 2.5, $q(K_{n+1}) = a \binom{n+1}{2} + (d - a) \binom{n}{2}$. Also since $q(K_{n+1}) = \binom{n+1}{2}$, we have $a = 1$ and $d = 1$. □

As it was mentioned in [3] that the complete graph K_{n+1} with $(n+1)$ vertices could easily be proved to have a star ASD and a path ASD, The converse follows.

Theorem 3.2 $K_{n,n}$ has (a, d) -ASD, $d \geq a$ if and only if $a = 1$ and $d = 2$.

Proof Suppose the graph $K_{n,n}$ admits $(a, d) - ASD$, $d \geq a$. If the graph $K_{n,n}$ admits $(a, d) - ASD$ $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ then by (ii) of Lemma 2.5, we have $|E(K_{n,n})| = a \binom{n+1}{2} + (d-a) \binom{n}{2}$.

Also, $|E(K_{n,n})| = n^2 = \binom{n+1}{2} + \binom{n}{2}$, so we have $a = 1$ and $d = 2$.

Conversely, suppose $a = 1, d = 2$.

Case (i) When n is even, $n = 2k, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Then $K_{n,n}$ can be decomposed into k -hamilton cycles $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_k$. Now, decompose the hamilton cycles H_i into paths G_i and $G_{n-(i-1)}$ of length $2i - 1$ and $2n - (2i - 1)$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$. Clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is the required $(1,2)$ -ASD of $K_{n,n}$.

Case (ii) When n is odd, $n = 2k + 1, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Let (X, Y) be the bipartition of $K_{n,n}$, where $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}, Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$. Define $H_1 = \{(x_n, y_j) : j = n-2\}$. For $2 \leq i \leq n-1$, define H_i by $H_{n+1-i} = \{(x_i, y_j) : j = 2i-2$ to $i+n-2\} \cup \{(x_j, y_{i+j-2}) : j = i+1$ to $n\}$, where addition is taken module n with residues $1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ instead of the usual residues $0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $H_n = \{(x_1, y_k) : k = 1, 2, \dots, n\} \cup \{(x_{j+1}, y_j) : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\}$. Clearly, $\{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n\}$ is a $(1, 2) - ASD$ of $K_{n,n}$. $\square$

Example 3.3 Consider the graph $K_{7,7}$. Let (X, Y) be the bipartition of $K_{7,7}$ where $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7\}, Y = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6, y_7\}$.

Fig. 3.1

Clearly, $\{H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7\}$ is $a(1, 2)$ -ASD of $K_{7,7}$.

Theorem 3.4 $K_{n,n}(n > 1)$ admits (a, d) -ASD, $d < a$ if and only if $n = 2a - 1$ and $d = 1, a > 1$.

Proof Suppose the graph $K_{n,n}(n > 1)$ admits (a, d) -ASD where $d < a$, then by (i) Lemma 2.5, we have $|E(K_{n,n})| = (a - d)n + d \binom{n+1}{2}$. Also, $|E(K_{n,n})| = n^2$. Therefore,

$$n^2 = (a - d)n + d \binom{n+1}{2} \text{ and so } (2 - d)n^2 = (2a - d)n. \text{ Then } n = \frac{2a-d}{2-d}.$$

Since, $n > 1, a > d$, we have $2 - d > 0$. Then $d = 1$ and $a > 1$. Hence $n = 2a - 1$.

Conversely, Suppose $n = 2a - 1, d = 1$ and $a > 1$. Let (X, Y) be the bipartition of $K_{n,n}$ where $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}, Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$.

Define $T_{n-j-1} = \{(x_j, y_i) : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{(y_{i-j+1}, x_i) : \frac{n+2j+1}{2} \leq i \leq n\}$ where $1 \leq j \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$ and $T_j = \{(x_{n-j+1}, y_i) : 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} + j\}$ where $1 \leq j \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$. Clearly, $\{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$ is the required $(a, 1)$ -ASD of $K_{n,n}$. $\square$

Example 3.5 Consider the graph $K_{5,5}$. Let (X, Y) be the bipartition of $K_{5,5}$ where $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5\}$. Clearly, $\{T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4, T_5\}$ is a $(3, 1)$ -ASD of $K_{5,5}$.

Fig. 3.2

§4. $(a, d) - ASD$ on Product Graphs

In this section, we prove some product graphs admit $(a, d) - ASD$.

Theorem 4.1 $C_n \times C_n (n > 3)$ has $(2, 4) - ASD$ when n is odd.

Proof Note that $|E(C_n \times C_n)| = 2n^2$ and $|V(C_n \times C_n)| = n^2$. By Theorem 1.2, The graph $C_n \times C_n$ (n -odd) can be decomposed into two Hamilton cycles C_1 and C_2 of length n^2 respectively.

Case (i) When $n = 2k + 1, k \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Let $P_1 = C_1 - (v, x)$ and $P_2 = C_2 - (v, y)$ where $v, x, y \in V(C_n \times C_n)$ and $x \neq y$. First, define $P_1 = (xvy)$ when $k = 3$, decompose the path P_1 into paths P_i of length $(4i - 2), 6 \leq i \leq 7$ and decompose the path P_2 into paths P_i of length $(4i - 2), 2 \leq i \leq 5$. For, $k > 4$, decompose the path P_1 into paths P_i of length $(4i - 2)$, where $2 \leq i \leq k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 1$ and $2 \left(2 - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) + \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1 \leq i \leq n$. Also decompose the path P_2 into paths P_i of length $(4i - 2)$, where $\left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) \leq i \leq 2 \left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) + \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor$. This is possible because of

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}(P_1^1) &= \sum_{j=1}^{k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 2} (2 + 4j) + \sum_{j=2 + (2(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor) + k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor)4}^{n-1} (2 + 4j) \\
&= \frac{(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 2)}{2} \left(12 + \left(\left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 2 \right) - 1 \right) 4 \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{(\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(2 + \left(2 \left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) + \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) 4 \right) + 4 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) \\
&= 2 \left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 2 \right) \left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) + \left(\frac{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1}{2} \right) \left(4 + 16k - 4 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \right) \\
&= 2k^2 - 4k - 4k \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 4 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 2 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor^2 + 2 + 8k + 8k \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 2 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor^2 \\
&= 2k^2 + 4k + 2 + 4k \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 4 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor \\
&= 2k^2 + 4k + 2 + 2k(k - 1) + 2(k - 1) \\
&= 4k^2 + 4k \\
&= (2k + 1)^2 - 1 = n^2 - 1 \\
\mathcal{L}(P_2') &= \left(\frac{k+1}{2} \right) \left(2 \left(2 + \left(k - \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 1 \right) 4 \right) + 4k \right) \\
&= (k + 1) \left(6k - 2 \left(2 \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + 1 \right) \right) \\
&= (k + 1)(6k - 2k) = (2k + 1)^2 - 1 = n^2 - 1.
\end{aligned}$$

From the above construction, clearly, $\{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$ is a $(2, 4) - ASD$ of $C_n \times C_n$.

Case (ii) When $n = 2k + 1, k \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

Let $P'_1 = C_1 - (v, x)$ and $P'_2 = C_2 - (v, y)$ where $v, x, y \in V(C_n \times C_n)$ and $x \neq y$. First define $P_1 = (xvy)$, then decompose the path P'_1 into paths P_2 of length 6 and P_j of length $(2 + 4j)$, $4 \leq j \leq n - 1$ and $j = 0, 1 \pmod{4}$ and also decompose the path P'_2 into paths P_j of length $(2 + 4j)$, $2 \leq j \leq n - 1$ and $j = 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. This is possible, since

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}(P'_1) &= 6 + \sum_{\substack{j=4 \\ j \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4}}}^{n-1} (2 + 4j) \\
&= 6 + 2 \sum_{\substack{j=4 \\ j \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4}}}^{n-1} 1 + 4 \sum_{\substack{j=4 \\ j \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4}}}^{n-1} j \\
&= 6 + 2 \sum_{\substack{j=4 \\ j \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4}}}^{2k} 1 + 4 \sum_{\substack{j=4 \\ j \equiv 0,1 \pmod{4}}}^{2k} j \\
&= 6 + 2(k - 1) + (4k^2 + 2k - 4) = (2k + 1)^2 - 1 = n^2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}(P'_2) &= \sum_{\substack{j=2 \\ j \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4}}}^{n-1} (2 + 4j) \\
&= 2 \sum_{\substack{j=2 \\ j \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4}}}^{2k} 1 + 4 \sum_{\substack{j=2 \\ j \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4}}}^{2k} j \\
&= 2k + 4 \sum_{\substack{j=2 \\ j \equiv 2,3 \pmod{4}}}^{2k} j \\
&= 2k + (2k + 4k^2) = (2k + 1)^2 - 1 = n^2 - 1.
\end{aligned}$$

As in the case clearly, $\{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$ is a $(2, 4)$ -ASD of $C_n \times C_n$. $\square$

Theorem 4.2 $P_{n+1} \times P_{n+1}$ with size $q = 2n(n + 1)$ admits $(4, 4)$ -ASD.

Proof Let $G = P_{n+1} \times P_{n+1}$. Define $W_{i,j} = (u_i, v_j)$, where $1 \leq i, j \leq n + 1$ and also define $V(G) = \{W_{i,j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq n + 1\}$, $|E(G)| = 2(n^2 + n)$.

Case (i) $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $n = 4m - 1$ ($m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$).

First define, $G_n = \{(W_{i,j}, V_{i,j+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq 4, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and define for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{n-3}{4}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_k &= \{(W_{i,j}, V_{i,j+1}) : i = 4k + 1, 1 \leq j \leq 4k\} \\
G_{n-k} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : i = 4k + 1, 4k + 1 \leq j \leq n \text{ and} \\
&\quad 4k + 2 \leq i \leq 4(k + 1), 1 \leq j \leq n\}
\end{aligned}$$

Also, define for $1 \leq \mathcal{L} \leq \frac{n+1}{4}$ and $k = \frac{n-3}{4}$.

$$G_{\mathcal{L}+k} = \{(W_{i,j}, V_{i+1,j}) : j = 4\mathcal{L} - 3, 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and} \\ j = 4\mathcal{L} - 2, 1 \leq i \leq 4\mathcal{L} - 3\}$$

$$G_{n-(\mathcal{L}+k)} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4\mathcal{L} - 2 \leq i \leq n, j = 4\mathcal{L} - 2 \text{ and} \\ 1 \leq i \leq n, 4\mathcal{L} - 1 \leq j \leq 4\mathcal{L}\}$$

Clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(4, 4)$ -ASD of $P_{n+1} \times P_{n+1}$ (See Fig. 4.1).

Fig. 4.1

Case (ii) $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $n = 4m$ ($m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$).

First define, $G_n = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq 4, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and define for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{n-4}{4}$.

$$G_k = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : i = 4k + 1, 1 \leq j \leq 4k\}$$

$$G_{n-k} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : i = 4k + 1, 4k + 1 \leq j \leq n \text{ and} \\ 4k + 2 \leq i \leq 4(k + 1), 1 \leq j \leq n\}$$

Define for $1 \leq \mathcal{L} \leq \frac{n-4}{4}$ and $p = \frac{n-4}{4}$.

$$G_{\mathcal{L}+p+1} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : j = 4\mathcal{L}, 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and} \\ j = 4\mathcal{L} + 1, 1 \leq i \leq 4\mathcal{L}\}$$

$$G_{n-(\mathcal{L}+p+1)} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4\mathcal{L} + 1 \leq i \leq n, j = 4\mathcal{L} + 1 \text{ and} \\ 1 \leq i \leq n, 4\mathcal{L} + 2 \leq j \leq 4\mathcal{L} + 3\}$$

$$G_{(p+1)} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : i = n + 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \text{ and}$$

$$G_{n-(p+1)} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 3\}$$

Finally define $G_{n/2} = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 1 \leq i \leq n, n \leq j \leq n+1\}$. From the above construction clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(4, 4)$ -ASD of $P_{n+1} \times P_{n+1}$ (See Fig. 4.2).

Fig 4.2

Case (iii) $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, n = 4m + 1 (m \in Z^+)$.

First define,

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_n &= \{(W_{i,j+1}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : i = 1, j = 1\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,i-1}W_{i,i}W_{i,i+1}W_{i-1,i}W_{i,i}W_{i+1,i}) : 2 \leq i \leq n\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j-1}W_{i,j}W_{i-1,j}) : i = n+1, j = n+1\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Define for $1 \leq r \leq \frac{n-5}{2}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{n-2r} &= \{(W_{i,j+1}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : i = 1, j = 2r+1\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j-1}W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}W_{i-1,j}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : 2 \leq i \leq n-2r \text{ and } j = 2r+i\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}W_{i+1,j-1}) : i = n-2r \text{ and } j = n+1\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, define for $r = \frac{n-3}{2}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 G'_2 &= \{(W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : i = 3, j = 2r+1\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}W_{i+1,j-1}) : i = n-2r, j = n+1\} \\
 G'_3 &= \{(W_{i,j+1}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : i = 1, j = 2r+1\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j-1}W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}W_{i-1,j}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}) : i = 2, j = 2r+i\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Define for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{n-3}{2}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 G'_{n-2k-1} &= \{(W_{i+1,j}W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}) : i = 1, j = 2k+1\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i-1,j}W_{i,j}W_{i+1,j}W_{i,j-1}W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}) : i = 2k+j \text{ and} \\
 &\quad 2 \leq j \leq n-2k-2\} \\
 &\cup \{(W_{i,j}W_{i,j+1}W_{i-1,j+1}) : i = n+1, j = n-2k-2\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$C_1 = (W_{1,n}, W_{2,n}, W_{2,n+1}, W_{1,n+1}, W_{1,n}),$$

$$C_2 = (W_{n,1}, W_{n+1,n}, W_{n+1,2}, W_{n,2}, W_{n,1}) \text{ and}$$

$$M = \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : i = 1, n + 1 \text{ and } j \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)\}$$

$$\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : j = 1, n + 1 \text{ and } i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)\}.$$

Let $G_{n-1} = G'_{n-1} \cup C_1$ and $G_{n-3} = G'_{n-3} \cup C_2$. Define $G_1 = M_0, G_2 = G'_2 \cup M_1, G_3 = G'_3 \cup M_2$ and $G_{n-2k+1} = G'_{n-2k-1} \cup M_k$, where $3 \leq k \leq \frac{n-3}{2}$ and $M_i \cong 4K_2$ are suitably chosen from M in order to form $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$ as $(4, 4) - ASD$ (See Fig 4.3).

Fig. 4.3

Case (iv) $n \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4), n = 4\mathcal{L} + 2(\mathcal{L} \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$.

For $1 \leq m \leq \mathcal{L}$ and $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_m &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 3 \leq i \leq 4m - 2, n + 2 - m \leq j \leq n + 1\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m + 1 \leq i \leq 4m - 2, n + 2 - m \leq j \leq n + 1\} \text{ and} \\ G_{n-(m-1)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 3 \leq i \leq 4m - 2 \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n + 1 - m\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m + 1 \leq i \leq 4m + 2 \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n + 1 - m\}. \end{aligned}$$

For $1 \leq m \leq \mathcal{L}$ and $m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_m &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 5 \leq i \leq 4m - 4, n + m - 2 \leq j \leq n + 1\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 1 \leq i \leq 4m, n + m - 2 \leq j \leq n + 1\} \text{ and} \\ G_{n-(m-1)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 5 \leq i \leq 4m - 4 \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n + m - 3\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 4m - 1 \leq i \leq 4m \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n + m - 3\}. \end{aligned}$$

For $1 \leq m \leq \mathcal{L}$ and $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_{m+\mathcal{L}} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : n - m - \mathcal{L} + 2 \leq i \leq n + 1 \text{ and} \\ &\quad 4m - 3 \leq j \leq 4m - 2\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : n - m - \mathcal{L} + 2 \leq i \leq n + 1 \text{ and} \\ &\quad 4m + 1 \leq j \leq 4m + 2\} \text{ and} \\ G_{n-(m+\mathcal{L}+1)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 1 \leq i \leq n - m - \mathcal{L} + 1 \text{ and } 4m - 3 \leq j \leq 4m - 2\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : 1 \leq i \leq n - m - \mathcal{L} + 1 \text{ and } 4m + 1 \leq i \leq 4m + 2\} \end{aligned}$$

and for $1 \leq m \leq \mathcal{L}$ and $m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{m+\mathcal{L}} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : n - m - \mathcal{L} + 3 \leq i \leq n + 1 \text{ and } 4m - 5 \leq j \leq 4m - 4\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : n - m - \mathcal{L} + 3 \leq i \leq n + 1 \text{ and } 4m - 1 \leq j \leq 4m\} \text{ and} \\ G_{n-(m+\mathcal{L}+1)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq n - m - \mathcal{L} - 2 \text{ and } 4m - 5 \leq j \leq 4m - 4\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq n - m - \mathcal{L} + 2 \text{ and } 4m - 1 \leq j \leq 4m\}. \end{aligned}$$

When $\mathcal{L}$ is even, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_{(n/2)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : 2 \leq i \leq n + 1, n - 1 \leq j \leq n\} \text{ and} \\ G_{(n/2)+1} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : n - 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \\ &\cup \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : i = 1, n - 1 \leq j \leq n\}. \end{aligned}$$

When $\mathcal{L}$ is odd, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_{(n/2)} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i,j+1}) : 2 \leq i \leq n + 1, n - 3 \leq j \leq n - 2\} \text{ and} \\ G_{(n/2)+1} &= \{(W_{i,j}, W_{i+1,j}) : n - 3 \leq i \leq n - 2 \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

From the above construction clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(4, 4)$ -ASD of $P_{n+1} \times P_{n+1}$. See Fig. 4.4(a) and Fig. 4.4(b). $\square$

Fig. 4.4(a)

Fig. 4.4(b)

§5. $(a, d) - ASD$ on Some Special Graphs

In this section $(a, d) - ASD$ is established for some special graphs like wheel, Carona and a special type in caterpillar.

Theorem 5.1 $W_{n^2+1} = K_1 + C_{n^2} (n \geq 3)$ has $(a, d) - ASD$, $d \geq a$ if and only if $a = 2$ and $d = 4$.

Proof Suppose W_{n^2+1} has $(a, d) - ASD$, $d \geq a$, By (ii) of Lemma 2.5, $|E(W_{n^2+1})| = a \binom{n+1}{2} + (d-a) \binom{n}{2}$, also we have $|E(W_{n^2+1})| = 2n^2$.

From the above relations, we have $a = 2$ and $d = 4$. Conversely, let $V(W_{n^2+1}) = \{u_1, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n^2}\}$. Define $G_1 = (u_1, v_1) \cup (v_1, v_2)$ and

$$G_i = \left\{ ((u_i, v_j) \cup (v_j, v_{j+1})) : \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} (2k-1) \leq j \leq \sum_{k=1}^i (2k-1) \right\}.$$

for $2 \leq i \leq n$. Where addition is taken modulo n^2 with residues $1, 2, 3, \dots, n^2$ instead of the usual residues $0, 1, 2, \dots, n^2 - 1$. Then clearly, $G_i \subseteq G_{i+1}$, $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ and $|E(G_i)| = 2(2i-1)$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Hence, $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(2, 4) - ASD$ of W_{n^2+1} . $\square$

Example 5.2 A decomposition of W_{n^2+1} , where $n = 3$ into $(2, 4) - ASD$ is illustrated in Fig. 5.1. Clearly, $\{G_1, G_2, G_3\}$ is a $(2, 4) - ASD$.

Fig. 5.1

Definition 5.3 Let $T = S(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n, v_{n+1})$ be a caterpillar where v_i means n leaves attached to each vertex and v_{n+1} means no leaf attached to the last vertex.

Theorem 5.4 The caterpillar $T = S(v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n-1}, v_n)$ has an $(a, d) - ASD$, ($d \geq a$) if and only if $a = 2$ and $d = 2$.

Proof Suppose T admits $(a, d) - ASD$ ($d \geq a$) By (ii) of Lemma 2.5, $|E(T)| = a \binom{n+1}{2} + (d-a) \binom{n}{2}$. Also, $|E(T)| = (n+1)n = n^2 + 1 = 2 \binom{n+1}{2}$. From the above two relations, we have $a = 2$ and $d = 2$.

Conversely, suppose $a = 2, d = 2$. Let

$$V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, v_{n+1}\} \cup \left\{ v_1^{(k)}, v_2^{(k)}, \dots, v_n^{(k)} : 1 \leq k \leq n \right\},$$

where v_i are vertices on the path P_n and $v_j^{(k)} (1 \leq k \leq n)$ are the vertices of the star at each $v_j (1 \leq j \leq n)$. Define for $1 \leq k \leq n, T_k = \{(v_k, v_{k+1})\} \cup \{(v_k, v_j^{(k)}) : 1 \leq j \leq n\}$.

Case (i) When n is odd, $n = 2m + 1$.

Decompose T_k for $k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{2}$ into G_m and $G_{n-(m-1)}, 1 \leq m \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$. Where

$$G_m = \{(v_{2k}, v_{2k+1})\} \cup \left\{ (v_{k+1}, v_j^{(k+1)}) : n - (2k - 2) \leq j \leq n \right\}$$

and

$$G_{n-(m-1)} = \left\{ (v_{k+1}, v_j^{(k)}) : 1 \leq j \leq n - (2k - 1) \right\} \cup \{(v_{2k-1}, v_{2k})\} \cup \left\{ (v_k, v_j^{(k)}) : 1 \leq j \leq n \right\}.$$

Define $G_{\frac{n+1}{2}} = \{(v_n, v_{n+1})\} \cup \left\{ (v_n, v_j^{(n)}) : 1 \leq j \leq n \right\}$. Clearly $G_i \subseteq G_{i+1}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $|E(G_i)| = 2i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Hence $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(2, 2) - ASD$ of T .

Case (ii) When n is even, $n = 2m$.

Decompose T_k for $k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$ into G_m and $G_{n-(m-1)}, 1 \leq m \leq \frac{n}{2}$ as in Case (i). Clearly $G_i \subseteq G_{i+1}, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$. Hence $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is a $(2, 2) - ASD$ of T . $\square$

Corollary 5.5 *The corona $C_n \odot nK_1$ has $(a, d) - ASD, (d \geq a)$ if and only if $a = 2$ and $d = 2$.*

Proof By taking $v_{n+1} = v_1$ in $T = S(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, v_{n+1})$. We have $T = C_n \odot nK_1$. $\square$

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